

Extractive Photometric Determination of Hydroxylamine

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An extractive spectrophotometric method is described for the determination of hydroxylamine. The colour reaction is based upon the well known diazotising and coupling reaction. Hydroxylamine is oxidised by iodine to nitrite, which diazotises with *p*-nitroaniline to form a diazonium salt, and then coupled with diphenylamine in acidic medium. The pink coloured chloroform extract dye has an absorption maxima at 540 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.00–0.16 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method are $3.30 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.001 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The optimum reaction conditions and other analytical parameters have been studied. The method has been applied for the determination of simple hydroxamic acids.

HYDROXYLAMINE and its derivatives have a common property to form methemoglobin in man and animal¹. It has also been detected in bacterial media and in tissues of a number of organisms². Hydroxylamine induces point mutations by reaction with cystosine, but in the presence of trace metals and oxygen it also produces radicals which rapidly inactivate DNA³. Hence, the determination of hydroxylamine in traces is very important both in industrial and biological studies. Hydroxylamine is chiefly employed as a reagent for detection and determination of various compounds and metals^{4–6}. Literature survey shows that hydroxylamine is usually determined by methods based on its oxidation or reduction; the most frequently employed being spectrophotometric methods either based on Griess–Illosvay reaction^{7–12} or involve direct reaction with hydroxylamine^{13–16}. Other available spectrophotometric methods are less sensitive and suffer from common interferences^{17–21}.

In the present communication a new and sensitive method is described for spectrophotometric determination of hydroxylamine. The method is based on the oxidation of hydroxylamine to nitrite by iodine²¹ in acetic acid medium. The nitrite so formed diazotises *p*-nitroaniline which is subsequently coupled with diphenylamine to give a pink coloured dye extractable in chloroform²². The chloroform extract of the dye has an absorption maxima at 540 nm. The colour is stable for more than 30 h. The system is sensitive, selective and is free from common interferents.

Experimental

All spectrophotometric measurements were done on ECIL GS 865 and Carl Zeiss Spekol spectrophotometers with 10 mm matched silica cells.

A stock solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride was prepared by dissolving A.R. grade hydroxyl-

amine hydrochloride in demineralised water. A working standard of $4 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ hydroxylamine was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock. A 0.05% (w/v) solution of *p*-nitroaniline solution was prepared in demineralised water. Iodine reagent was prepared by dissolving iodine (1.3 g) in glacial acetic acid (100 ml). A 2.5% (w/v) solution of sodium thiosulphate was prepared in demineralised water. A 0.2% (w/v) solution of diphenylamine was prepared in 10 *M* glacial acetic acid. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Deionised water was used for preparing solutions.

Procedure: An aliquot (~50 ml) of sample containing 0–8 μg hydroxylamine was taken in a 100 ml graduated boiling tube. Sodium acetate–acetic acid solution (1 ml) and *p*-nitroaniline solution (3 ml) were added to the sample solution. To it iodine reagent (2 ml) was added, shaken and allowed to stand for 2–5 min to ensure complete diazotisation. The acidity was adjusted to 1 *M* with HCl. Excess of iodine was removed by dropwise addition of sodium thiosulphate solution. Diphenylamine solution (2 ml) was then added and the acidity adjusted to 2.5 *M*. The solution was then thermostated for 60 min at 60° and was transferred to a separatory funnel and extracted with chloroform in small portions. The brown coloured chloroform extract was shaken with HCl (0.5 ml) which turned pink on addition of the acid. The pink coloured chloroform layer was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask and made upto the mark with glacial acetic acid. The absorbance was measured at 540 nm against a chloroform blank.

Results and Discussion

Iodine oxidation of hydroxylamine takes place according to

at pH 2.2–3.0 maintained by the addition of acetic acid–sodium acetate solution. The oxidation of

hydroxylamine to nitrite was completed within 2 min.

p-Nitroaniline reacts with nitrite to form *p*-nitrophenyl diazonium chloride which is then coupled with diphenylamine. For coupling, the most suitable acidity range was found to be 1.5–3.5 *M* with respect to HCl. The diazotisation reaction was fast at room temperature and it was complete within 1 min. The temperature required for coupling was studied by developing colour at different temperatures from 50 to 80° for 60 min. Best results were obtained at 60°. Below 50° the colour reaction was found to be incomplete. The colour of the extract was found to be stable for 30 h. Chloroform was found to be most suitable among the various solvents tried, *viz.* isoamyl alcohol, benzene, hexanol, *n*-octanol. Extraction in chloroform enabled to determine sub-micrograms of hydroxylamine in large volume of sample.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and reproducibility: The colour system was found to obey Beer's law in the range of 0–8 µg per 50 ml (0.0–0.16 ppm) of the sample. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.30 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.001 µg cm^{-2} respectively. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.014 and 0.2%, respectively.

Interferences: 6 µg/50 ml of hydroxylamine was determined in presence of known amount of interferents like hydrazine, aniline, phenol, hydrocarbons, Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} , phosphite *etc.* The tolerance limit in (ppm) with $\pm 2\%$ error were as follows: aniline (100), hydrazine (1 000), phenylhydrazine (1 000), hydrocarbons (2 500), formaldehyde (2 000), benzaldehyde (2 000), ethanol (200), phenol (2 000), 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (1 500), Cu^{II} (600), Ca^{II} (600), Mg^{II} (400), Fe^{III} (900), Zn^{II} (2 000), ammonia (400) and phosphate (2 000).

Determination of benzohydroxamic acid:

An aliquot of sample (~50 ml) containing 10–80 µg of benzohydroxamic acid was taken in a 100 ml graduated boiling tube. Sodium acetate–acetic acid solution (1 ml) and *p*-nitroaniline solution (3 ml) were added to the sample. To it iodine reagent (2 ml) was added and allowed to stand for 2 min to ensure complete diazotisation. Excess of iodine was removed by dropwise addition of sodium thiosulphate solution. Diphenylamine solution (2 ml) was then added and acidity was adjusted to ~2.5 *M* with HCl. The solution was thermostated for 1 h at 60° and was then transferred to a separatory funnel and extracted with chloroform. The pink coloured chloroform extract was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask and the absorbance measured at 540 nm against a chloroform blank.

Effect of pH: Benzohydroxamic acid is directly oxidised to nitrite. Iodine oxidation of the sample was found maximum at pH 5.5–6.5.

Beer's law, reproducibility, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity: The colour system obeys Beer's law in the range of 10–80 µg/50 ml. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $16.3 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0025 \text{ µg cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Comparison with other methods: The present method has been found to be more sensitive than other reported methods (Table 1).

TABLE 1—COMPARISON WITH OTHER COLOURIMETRIC REAGENTS

Sl. no.	Reagents for hydroxylamine	Limit of determination
1.	Triphenyl tetrazolium chloride ^a	25 µg/ml
2.	1-(Naphthyl)ethylene diamine dihydrochloride ^b	0–8 µg/25 ml
3.	Ferrozene ^c	1–10 µg/25 ml
4.	8-Quinolinol ^d	0.2–100 µg
5.	Tetracyanophenanthroline ferrate ^e	8–80 µg/10 ml
6.	<i>o</i> -Diamisidine ^f	0.1–4 µg/ml
7.	Diphenylamine ^g	0–8 µg/50 ml

^a Ref. 10. ^b Ref. 12. ^c Ref. 13. ^d Ref. 16. ^e Ref. 18.
^f Ref. 20. ^g Present study (extractive).

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